

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Hoxd4.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Hoxd4 as a candidate
9 gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

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12 R.R., 1995. Compound mutants for the paralogous hoxa-4, hoxb-4, and hoxd-4 genes show more
13 complete homeotic transformations and a dose-dependent increase in the number of vertebrae
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